

DMP for SustainAgriFinTech Project

Version 1

Description

SustainAgriFinTech: Integrating Smart Digital Solutions for Sustainable Farming Systems and Finance through Life Cycle Assessment and Environmental, Social, and Governance Metrics.

This industrial, non-economic research project spans 36 months at the Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies (LBTU) and aims to develop an innovative at least TRL2 level IT/mobile application prototype to help farmers assess their transition to sustainable agriculture – specifically organic farming, agroecology, regenerative agriculture, and permaculture. The tool will integrate digital solutions, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) criteria, and sustainable finance instruments to provide tailored recommendations and funding options. Aligned with the RIS3 priority of a knowledge-intensive bioeconomy within Economics and Business.

Expected outcomes include at least a TRL 2 level prototype, a stakeholder seminar, two Q1/Q2- indexed journal publications, six additional scientific articles, six international conference presentations, and eight short-term mobility exchanges.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

SustainAgriFinTech: Integrating Smart Digital Solutions for Sustainable Farming Systems and Finance through Life Cycle Assessment and

Environmental, Social, and
Governance Metrics - Project
No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/220

Researchers

Aija Pilvere (orcid:0000-0001-7422-6115)

Organizations

Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [DMP for SustainAgriFinTech Project](#)

Description:

SustainAgriFinTech: Integrating Smart Digital Solutions for Sustainable Farming Systems and Finance through Life Cycle Assessment and Environmental, Social, and Governance Metrics.

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Researchers:

[Aija Pilvere \(orcid:0000-0001-7422-6115\)](#)

Organizations:

[Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies](#)

Contact: [Pilvere Aija \(ajija.pilvere@lbtu.lv\)](mailto:pilvere.ajija@lbtu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science | | LCS](#)

Grants: [SustainAgriFinTech: Integrating Smart Digital Solutions for Sustainable Farming Systems and Finance through Life Cycle Assessment and Environmental, Social, and Governance Metrics - Project No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/220](#)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Dataset of SustainAgriFinTech project

Data will be on the whole project SustainAgriFinTech: Integrating Smart Digital Solutions for Sustainable Farming Systems and Finance through Life Cycle Assessment and Environmental, Social, and Governance Metrics. Compiled data on the framework and the study. It is intended to be used to create the structure for the TRL 2 level prototype and research.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data will be collected during the the whole project SustainAgriFinTech: Integrating Smart Digital Solutions for Sustainable Farming Systems and Finance through Life Cycle Assessment and Environmental, Social, and Governance Metrics. It is intended to be used to create the structure for the TRL 2 level prototype and research articles.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Aggregate data
- Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PDF
- CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Prior to the start of the study, relevant datasets and publications on the research topic were reviewed. No publicly available datasets were identified that would provide comprehensive and context-specific information on the study objectives. Therefore, it was considered necessary to conduct new data collection.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Stakeholders, researchers and policymakers.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Due to the sensitive nature of the survey, participants' only combined and aggregated answers will be provided as well as when commercially sensitive data is used, the rest of the cases, when nonsensitive or non commercial data is used as metadata, it will be open access.

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

If dataset is created before article is published, the embargo period will be enforced until the research article that uses the dataset is published.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

<https://dv.dataverse.lv/>

DataverseLV was selected as the repository because it is a trusted, institutionally supported platform that ensures long-term preservation and open access to

research data in compliance with FAIR principles. It provides persistent identifiers (DOIs) via DataCite, supports rich metadata, and allows for the inclusion of accompanying documentation and code. The platform is aligned with Latvian and European open science policies and ensures data discoverability through international indexing services.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The dataset will be provided in CSV format, which can be opened with standard spreadsheet software (e.g., Microsoft Excel, OpenOffice Calc) or any text editor, and in PDF format, which can be accessed with widely available PDF readers (e.g., Adobe Acrobat Reader). No specialized software is required.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The CSV format is a non-proprietary, machine-readable format that is widely supported by data analysis, spreadsheet, and statistical software, enabling interoperability and integration with other datasets. The PDF format used for documentation is an open standard (ISO 32000) and can be accessed by a wide range of applications. Both formats facilitate long-term accessibility and reuse without dependence on specific proprietary software.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

The dataset will be released under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 (CC BY-NC 4.0) license to allow free access, sharing, and reuse for non-commercial purposes while ensuring that the original creators are properly credited. This license balances openness with protection against commercial exploitation.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2029-03-20

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2031-03-20

Data gets outdated fast.

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Project budget.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Aija Pilvere (orcid: [0000-0001-7422-6115](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7422-6115))

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

After the project's completion, the resources required for long-term data preservation, access, and management — including the repository, its services,

and human resources — will be financed by the Higher Education and Science Information Technology Shared Service Centre.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Anonymising data
- Privacy constraints
- Pseudonymization

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